

Non-equilibrium growth patterns in a reaction between thiamine and glucose

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Abstract : Reaction between glucose and thiamine has been studied in aqueous solution containing gel matrix. Growth patterns of the reactants and the product have been studied. Glucose crystallizes in the form of fractal with fractal dimension 1.74 and thiamine as spherulitic when observed under polarized light microscope. Glucose-thiamine reaction product crystallized in different morphologies. Following transitions were observed on increasing the concentration.

Spherulite → Ringed spherulite → Revert spaced concentric rings

Besides change in the morphology of the reaction product, XRD, IR and DSC studies also revealed the formation of a new product. During the reaction glucose was continuously consumed on addition of thiamine, obeying the relation $[G]^{-1} = m \log V + c$, where m and c are slope and intercept respectively. Heat of fusion ΔH of the product was calculated using the expression $\Delta H.m = KA$, where m is the mass of the substance, K and A are the calibration constant and area under the curve respectively. The value was found to be 1.36 kcal/mol, which was lower than those of the individual reactants.

Keywords : Growth pattern, fractal, biomaterial, Schiff base.

Introduction

Pattern formation has fascinated mankind for many years. Recently the study of growing structures has developed mainly due to the development of the concept of fractal geometry¹ and computer stimulations. Irreversible aggregation of small particles to form large clusters, which can be seen in many fields including science and technology, is attracting scientists of the world. Examples are many and ranging from the growth of a snowflake to the electrochemical growth², bacterial growth³, crystal growth⁴, viscous fingering⁵ and dielectric breakdown. Besides this, the chemistry of saccharides has emerged as a new sub area. Amino acid and analogous compounds containing amino group are indispensable basic components in biology and possibly take part in sensing processes⁶. There is considerable interest in the study of Schiff base reaction⁷. During glycation, glucose reacts covalently with basic amino acid to form Schiff base⁸. The Millard reaction⁹ initiated by non-enzymatic glycation of amino group by reducing sugars has been studied for its potential role in aging and the complication in diabetes.

In the present paper, we report reaction between glu-

cose and nitrogenous compounds such as thiamine hydrochloride, change in growth morphologies and results of XRD, FT-IR and DSC studies.

Experimental

Materials : D-Glucose (Qualigens), thiamine hydrochloride (Fluka), agar-agar (Difco, Bacteriological grade) were used as such.

Procedure :

Growth morphologies and computation of fractal dimension D :

Growth morphologies of glucose and glucose containing thiamine were investigated at different experimental conditions. For this purpose, 1 ml of aqueous solution of glucose 0.01 M, thiamine 0.01 M and mixture of glucose and thiamine were spread over micro slides and kept in an incubator at 37.0 ± 0.1 °C to crystallize. The dried micro slides were observed under 'OLYMPUS' Polarized Light Microscope and microphotographs were taken. Results are shown in Fig. 1. Experiment was performed at different concentrations and results are shown in Fig. 2.

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

(c)

(c)

Fig. 1. Microphotographs of (a) aqueous solution of glucose (0.01 *M*) containing 0.2% agar-agar, (b) thiamine (0.01 *M*) containing 0.2% agar-agar and (c) glucose containing thiamine (0.01 *M*) and 0.2% agar-agar.

Fig. 2. Growth pattern of glucose and thiamine reaction product in 1 : 1 molar ratio at different concentrations containing 0.2% agar-agar. [Glucose] = [Thiamine] = (a) 0.01 *M*, (b) 0.04 *M* and (c) 0.06 *M*.

For the computation of fractal dimension D of the growth pattern shown in Fig. 1(a), microphotograph was scanned with the help of a Scanner attached to a computer (HP, PCAT 486 Model Vectra VL2). The fractal dimension of the picture was determined by box counting method. The log-log plot of $N(r)$, the total number of

boxes inside a circle of radius (r) versus r was made. The fractal dimension D is given by the slope of the best fitted straight line using least square method of analysis.

X-Ray diffraction and IR studies :

X-Ray diffraction patterns of glucose, thiamine and glucose-thiamine reaction product were taken using Bruker

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction patterns of (a) thiamine, (b) reaction product of glucose with thiamine and (c) glucose.

XR diffraction model D-8. Results are shown in Fig. 3.

The FT-IR spectrum of glucose-thiamine complex was recorded using KBr pellet. Results are shown in Fig. 4.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) :

Thermal characteristics of glucose, thiamine and glucose-thiamine reaction product were investigated by using Mettler Toledo differential scanning calorimeter model DSC 821 in the temperature range 60 to 500 °C. Results are shown in Fig. 5.

Estimation of glucose concentration :

Dependence of glucose concentration on the volume of thiamine was estimated volumetrically using the stan-

dard method¹⁰. A standard solution of glucose (200 mg%) was prepared in double distilled water. Equal volumes of Fehling solutions A and B were mixed in a dry flask and shaken thoroughly. 25 ml of this freshly mixed Fehling solution was taken in porcelain dish and diluted it with 25 ml water. The solution was boiled gently. Standard solution of glucose (200 mg%) was prepared and taken in the burette and titrated with boiling Fehling solution until the blue colour has completely disappeared. Concentration of glucose in the presence of thiamine at different volume was estimated using this method. Plot of glucose concentration as a function of volume of thiamine is shown in Fig. 6.

Results and discussion

The glucose-thiamine reaction contributes to be well known non-enzymatic reaction similar to the reactions between the amino acids and sugars to form Schiff's base as shown in Scheme 1.

The presence of an imino center in the reaction product was confirmed by FT-IR study (Fig. 4). The product showed a sharp $\nu_{C=N}$ stretching vibration at 1606.5 cm^{-1} and 1660 cm^{-1} supporting the formation of the imino center. Estimating the glucose concentration volumetrically as a function of volume of thiamine followed the above reaction. On account of the reaction there is a continuous decrease in glucose concentration as a function of volume of thiamine. Results show that glucose concentration $[G]$ depends on the volume V of the thiamine and obey the relation $[G]^{-1} = m \log V + c$, where m and c are slope and intercept respectively.

The formation of a new product was established by X-ray diffraction studies. X-Ray diffraction patterns and five intense lines of thiamine, glucose and its reaction product are shown in Fig. 3 and recorded in Table 1. Results show that the pattern of the product is different from those of the individual reactants. The product has smaller particle size as evident by broadening of peak in the X-ray diffraction pattern of the product.

Thermal characteristics of the reaction product and individual reactants have been studied and the results are shown in Fig. 5. Endotherms at 157, 256 and 169 °C correspond to melting points of glucose, thiamine and reaction product respectively. Heat of fusion of thiamine, glucose and the reaction product were determined by com-

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectrum of the reaction product of thiamine and glucose.

Scheme 1

Fig. 5. DSC thermograms of (a) thiamine, (b) reaction product of glucose with thiamine and (c) glucose.

paring their peak areas with that of benzoic acid of which the heat of fusion is (3.87 kcal/mol) using the expression

$$\Delta H.m = KA$$

where ΔH is the heat of fusion, m the mass of sample, K

Fig. 6. Plot of glucose concentration as a function of volume of thiamine. Conditions : [glucose] = 200 mg%, [thiamine] = 0.01 M.

Table 1. Five intense lines in X-ray diffraction patterns of glucose, thiamine and the reaction product of glucose and thiamine

Glucose		Thiamine		Reaction product of glucose and thiamine	
2 θ	I/I^0	2 θ	I/I^0	2 θ	I/I^0
12.788	40	8.488	61	25.351	34
19.801	100	16.849	41	32.232	69
20.250	89	23.402	51	32.580	87
22.827	61	26.925	50	34.041	100
28.383	40	27.956	100	36.270	74

the calibration coefficient and A is the peak area.

Heat of fusion of glucose, thiamine and the reaction product were found to be 3.78, 5.36 and 1.36 kcal/mol respectively. Results indicate that the product is different from the individual reactants, has the higher thermal stability than the reactants and lower heat of fusion than those of reactants.

Microphotographs of glucose, thiamine and the product of reaction between glucose and thiamine in agar-agar matrix are shown in Fig. 1. Morphology of the reaction product was different from those of individual reactants. Glucose crystallizes in the form of fractal (Fig. 1a) with a fractal dimension 1.74, thiamine as the spherulite (Fig. 1b) while the reaction product has structure diffe-

rent from (a) and (b). Fig. 2 shows microphotographs of thiamine and glucose when admixed in different concentrations in 1 : 1 molar ratio and containing 0.2% agar-agar and spread over micro slides in equal volume in each case. Interesting observations were the transitions from spherulitic to banded spherulite. Saracovan *et al.*¹¹ have also observed similar results in case of polymers and finally to revert spaced concentric rings on increasing the concentration. Such transitions may be due to change in growth speed.

Conclusion :

We observe that glucose reacts with thiamine to form a product, which is different from the individual reactants as evident by difference in growth patterns, XRD, IR and DSC. The heat of fusion of the product was determined and found to be 3.87 kcal/mol. Dependence of glucose concentration on thiamine obey the empirical equation $[G]^{-1} = m \log V + c$. Growth morphology of the product was found to depend on concentration and following transitions were observed.

Spherulite → Ringed spherulite →

Revert spaced concentric rings

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